

Research Article

Genetic Diversity and Prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* in Rivers State, Nigeria: A Comparison of Conventional Diagnostic and Molecular Method

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Abstract

Background: Malaria, caused by *Plasmodium falciparum*, remains a major health challenge, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Accurate diagnosis is essential for effective treatment and control, yet the performance of diagnostic techniques varies, especially in resource-limited settings.

Objective: This study aimed to compare the prevalence of *P. falciparum* using three diagnostic methods—Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT), microscopy, and Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)—and to determine the genetic diversity of *P. falciparum* in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Methodology: A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted at two health facilities in Rivers State. A total of 500 febrile patients were enrolled, and blood samples were tested using RDT, microscopy, and PCR. Genetic analysis was performed using the two major Merozoite Surface Protein (MSP1 and MSP2) using molecular techniques.

Results: The prevalence of *P. falciparum* was highest with PCR (52.4%), followed by microscopy (51.0%) and RDT (41.6%). Bori Zonal Hospital exhibited a higher prevalence than Nchia General Hospital across all diagnostic methods. Genetic analysis revealed significant diversity in *P. falciparum* subtypes, with MSP2B being the most prevalent in Bori (18.8%) and Nchia (9.6%).

Conclusion: PCR had the highest detection rate, followed by microscopy and RDT. Bori Zonal Hospital had a higher prevalence, and MSP2B was the most common subtype. These findings highlight the value of molecular techniques in malaria surveillance.

1. Introduction

Malaria remains a major public health challenge in many tropical and subtropical regions, with *Plasmodium falciparum* responsible for the most severe forms of the disease and the majority of malaria-associated morbidity and mortality worldwide. The parasite invades and multiplies within erythrocytes, provoking host immune responses and the characteristic clinical manifestations of malaria; among *Plasmodium* species that infect humans, *P. falciparum* is most frequently linked to severe and sometimes fatal disease [1]. Globally and within Nigeria, children and pregnant women bear a disproportionate share of the burden, and the epidemiology of infection is shaped by a complex interplay of host immunity, parasite biology, vector ecology and local environmental conditions [2, 3].

Accurate laboratory diagnosis of malaria is central to effective case management, surveillance and control. Historically, light microscopy of Giemsa-stained blood films has been the cornerstone of parasitological diagnosis because it permits species identification and parasite

quantification features that are important for treatment decisions and epidemiologic surveillance [4]. However, the reliability of microscopy is highly dependent on the availability of experienced personnel, quality reagents, and stable laboratory infrastructure; in many endemic and resource-limited settings, inadequate training and intermittent power supply undermine microscopy quality and reduce its diagnostic sensitivity and specificity.

Rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) were introduced to extend parasitological diagnosis to peripheral and resource-poor health settings where microscopy is unavailable or unreliable. RDTs are user-friendly, rapid and do not require electricity or specialised equipment, and many available products target *P. falciparum*-specific antigens such as histidine-rich protein 2 (HRP2) or parasite lactate dehydrogenase (pLDH) [5, 6]. Despite these advantages, RDTs have recognised limitations: HRP2-based tests may produce false-positive results due to persistent antigenemia after parasite clearance, while gene deletions and low parasite densities can result in false negatives [4, 7]. Consequently, RDTs should be interpreted in the context of clinical findings and, where possible, confirmed by alternative diagnostic approaches.

Molecular methods, particularly polymerase chain reaction (PCR), have emerged as highly sensitive and specific tools for malaria detection. PCR techniques can detect very low-density parasitemia (as few as 1–5 parasites/ μ L), identify mixed infections and provide genetic information useful for surveillance, treatment monitoring and the detection of drug-resistant parasites [8, 9]. These attributes make PCR an attractive reference standard in research and specialised diagnostic settings. Nevertheless, routine implementation of PCR in many endemic countries is constrained by cost, technical complexity and the need for well-equipped laboratories and trained personnel [10].

Beyond simple detection, characterising the genetic diversity of *P. falciparum* within communities provides important epidemiologic insight. Merozoite surface proteins, principally MSP1 and MSP2, are polymorphic antigens commonly used to genotype parasite populations. Variation in MSP allelic families reflect local transmission intensity, multiplicity of infection and patterns of genetic recombination and has implications for vaccine design and for understanding the evolution of parasite traits such as drug resistance [11, 12]. Previous studies in Nigeria have shown heterogeneous distributions of MSP alleles across regions, indicating spatial variability in parasite population structure [13].

Rivers State, situated in Nigeria's Niger Delta, represents a setting where environmental factors, population movement and varying access to health services may influence malaria transmission and diagnostic outcomes. In routine clinical practice within the state, microscopy and RDTs remain the most commonly used diagnostics, while molecular methods are less accessible. Consequently, evaluating how these diagnostic techniques compare in detecting *P. falciparum* and documenting the circulating MSP subtypes is essential to understanding the true burden of infection and to inform diagnostic and control strategies.

This study therefore aimed to examine, within two health facilities in Rivers State, the prevalence of *P. falciparum* as determined by three commonly used diagnostic modalities—RDT, microscopy and PCR—and to characterize the distribution of *P. falciparum* MSP subtypes among PCR-positive samples. By restricting analyses to facility-based febrile patients and by comparing test outcomes and subtype distributions across locations, the study seeks to shed light on the relative performance of routine diagnostics and on the genetic diversity of *P. falciparum* circulating in this endemic setting.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Area

The study was carried out in two health facilities located in Rivers State, Nigeria: Bori Zonal Hospital in Khana Local Government Area and Nchia (Eleme) General Hospital in Eleme Local Government Area. These areas lie within the rainforest ecological zone of the Niger Delta, characterised by high rainfall, elevated humidity, and temperatures ranging from 25°C to 28°C, all of which favour intense malaria transmission. Bori Zonal Hospital is situated at approximately latitude 4.67300°N and longitude 7.37650°E, while Eleme General Hospital lies at latitude 4.78410°N and longitude 7.14020°E.

2.2. Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Rivers State Hospitals Management Board. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was secured from all eligible individuals or their guardians. Anonymity and confidentiality were ensured throughout the study.

2.3. Study Design and Population

A hospital-based cross-sectional study design was adopted. The study population consisted of febrile patients presenting at the outpatient departments of the two facilities between June and October 2022. Individuals aged between 2 and 50 years who had an axillary temperature above 37.5°C and consented to participate were enrolled. A total of 500 patients were recruited from both locations, representing a mix of males and females, predominantly comprising rural dwellers, peasant farmers, and individuals engaged in informal occupations.

2.4. Sample Collection

Four milliliters of venous blood were collected aseptically from each participant using sterile syringes and transferred into EDTA anticoagulant bottles. Each sample was coded to eliminate personal identifiers. The samples were promptly transported to the Medical Laboratory Unit of Bori Zonal Hospital for processing.

2.5. Microscopic Examination

Microscopy was used to screen for the presence of *Plasmodium falciparum* parasites. Thick and thin blood films were prepared from each sample. Thick films were stained with Giemsa stain, while thin films were stained with Leishman stain. Trained Medical Laboratory Scientists examined the stained slides under $\times 100$ oil immersion objective. A minimum of 200 high-power fields was observed before a slide was considered negative. Positive detections of *P. falciparum* were recorded accordingly.

2.6. Rapid Diagnostic Test Procedure

Rapid diagnostic testing was conducted using First Response Malaria Ag pLDH/HRP2 Combo kits and Micro point Pf Ag test cassettes. Five microliters of whole blood were applied to the sample window, followed by two drops of assay buffer. Results were read after 20 minutes following the manufacturers' interpretation guidelines. The appearance of both control and test lines signified a positive result, while the presence of only the control line indicated a negative result.

2.7. DNA Extraction

Genomic DNA was extracted from whole blood using a Zymo-spin column-based extraction method. Whole blood samples were lysed with genomic lysis buffer, vortexed, and allowed to stand for five minutes at room temperature. The lysate was transferred into labelled spin columns and centrifuged. Prewash and g-DNA wash buffers were applied sequentially to remove impurities, and DNA was eluted with 90 μ L of elution buffer. The extracted DNA served as template for molecular detection and genotyping.

2.8. PCR Detection of *Plasmodium falciparum*

Polymerase chain reaction was used to confirm the presence of *P. falciparum* DNA. Primary PCR amplification targeted conserved regions of MSP1 and MSP2 genes using gene-specific primers. The reaction mixture contained DreamTaq master mix, forward and reverse primers, and extracted DNA. The thermocycling conditions for MSP1 amplification involved an initial denaturation at 95°C, followed by denaturation at 94°C, annealing at 61°C, and extension at 72°C for the required cycles. MSP2 amplification followed similar conditions with adjustments to the annealing temperature and cycle duration as specified for its primer set. Amplified products indicating the presence of *P. falciparum* were documented.

2.9. Nested PCR for MSP1 and MSP2 Subtyping

Nested PCR was performed on all samples that tested positive during primary PCR to determine the specific allelic families of MSP1 and MSP2 circulating in the population. For MSP1, the secondary amplification targeted distinct allelic families, while for MSP2, nested reactions differentiated the major allelic subtypes. Amplicon sizes corresponding to each family were used to classify the subtypes present.

2.10. Gel Electrophoresis and Visualization

PCR and nested PCR products were separated on agarose gels and visualised under ultraviolet illumination. Band sizes were compared with a molecular weight ladder to determine the presence and identity of MSP1 and MSP2 alleles. These electrophoretic profiles were used to establish both molecular positivity and subtype distribution across the study locations.

2.11. Data Handling and Analysis

Data generated from microscopy, RDT, PCR, and MSP subtyping were systematically recorded, coded, and entered for analysis. Prevalence of *P. falciparum* was determined based on the proportion of positive detections by each diagnostic method. Subtype frequencies were computed by determining the number of samples exhibiting specific MSP1 and MSP2 alleles within each study location.

3. Results

Table 1: Prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* among the studied population based on the outcomes of the three diagnostic techniques

	RDT		PCR		MICROSCOPY		TOTAL	
	No Examined	No infected n(%)						
Bori	250	111 (44.4)	250	157 (62.8)	250	152 (60.8)	750	420(56.0)
Nchia	250	97 (38.6)	250	105 (42.0)	250	103 (41.2)	750	305(40.7)
Total	500	208(41.6)	500	262(52.4)	500	255(51.0)	1500	725(48.3)
P-value		0.3198		0.0057		0.0069		
Chi Square		0.9899		7.642		7.293		

Legend: RDT= Rapid Diagnostic Test, PCR = Polymerase Chain Reaction

The prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* among the studied population, as detected by three diagnostic techniques (RDT, PCR, and microscopy), showed variation across the two study locations. A total of 500 participants were examined at each location. The highest detection rate was observed with PCR, identifying 262 positive cases (52.4%), followed by microscopy with 255 positive cases (51.0%), and RDT with 208 positive cases (41.6%). Bori Zonal Hospital had a higher prevalence of *P. falciparum* than Nchia General Hospital across all three diagnostic techniques, with 56.0% of participants testing positive in Bori and 40.7% in Nchia. The statistical analysis indicated significant differences between PCR and both RDT ($p = 0.0057$) and microscopy ($p = 0.0069$), but no significant difference was found between RDT and microscopy ($p = 0.3198$) are shown in Table 1.

Table 2: Prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* Subtypes based on Study Location

Location	Subtypes of <i>Malaria falciparum</i> (%)				
	IK	IM	IR	2A	2B
Bori (n=250)	27 (10.8)	25(10.0)	28 (11,2)	30 (12.0)	47 (18.8)
Nchia (n=250)	22(8.8)	21(8.4)	19(7.6)	17(6.8)	26(9.6)
Total (n=500)	49 (9.8)	46 (9.2)	47 (9.4)	47 (9.4)	73 (14.6)
P-value	0.8869	2.426	0.1813	0.4675	<0.0001
Chi-square	0.02024	0.1193	0.603	0.5279	53.63

The prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* subtypes based on study location is presented in Table 2. Among the 250 participants from Bori Zonal Hospital, the most prevalent subtype was MSP2B (47, 18.8%), followed by MSP1 (28, 11.2%), and MSP2A (30, 12.0%). In Nchia General Hospital, the most common subtype was also MSP2B (26, 9.6%), with MSP1 (22, 8.8%) and MSP2A (19, 7.6%) following. The total prevalence across both locations showed a higher frequency of MSP2B (73, 14.6%) compared to other subtypes. The statistical analysis revealed a significant difference in the prevalence of MSP2B between the two locations ($p < 0.0001$), while other subtypes did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 2: Agarose Gel Electrophoresis of some Amplified representative MSP1 genes of some selected malaria blood samples. Lane 10 represents the MSP1 gene band (390bp). Lane T represents the 100bp Molecular ladder of 1500bp.

4. Discussion

The assessment of *Plasmodium falciparum* prevalence using RDT, microscopy and PCR in this study demonstrated notable variations across diagnostic approaches, reflecting the inherent strengths and limitations of each method. PCR recorded the highest prevalence, which aligns with its established role as the most sensitive technique for malaria detection due to its ability to identify very low parasitaemia and mixed infections that may escape conventional diagnostics [8, 9]. The molecular detection of parasite DNA also circumvents challenges associated with antigen persistence and operator subjectivity, offering a more reliable measure of true infection burden in endemic populations.

Microscopy, although less sensitive than PCR, performed better than RDTs. This finding is consistent with the long-held position that microscopy remains a dependable tool when conducted by experienced personnel using properly stained and prepared slides [4]. Its ability to detect different life stages and quantify parasites gives it advantages in clinical settings. However, its performance can decline in low-density infections and in environments where training and laboratory resources are inconsistent, potentially explaining the cases that PCR detected but microscopy did not.

RDTs recorded the lowest prevalence, a result also reported in several malaria-endemic settings where antigen-based tests underperform in detecting low-level infections or infections involving HRP2 deletion variants [7]. Persistent antigenemia following parasite clearance may

also cause false positives, while low parasite densities compromise test sensitivity. These limitations highlight the challenges of relying solely on RDTs for surveillance or epidemiological assessments, especially in rural settings where test quality, storage conditions, and operator experience may vary.

The difference in infection rates between Bori and Eleme further provides insight into location-specific malaria transmission dynamics. Bori consistently showed higher positivity across all diagnostic methods, suggesting a more intense transmission environment. Such variation within relatively close geographical areas is not unusual, as malaria transmission is influenced by micro-climatic conditions, vegetation, mosquito breeding sites, human movement patterns, and socio-economic activities [1, 3]. The higher parasite burden in Bori may reflect differences in environmental suitability for Anopheles vectors or disparities in access to preventive measures and healthcare services.

The analysis of MSP1 and MSP2 allelic families revealed substantial genetic diversity within the *P. falciparum* population across the study sites. Polymorphism in MSP genes is a hallmark of *P. falciparum* populations in high-transmission settings, driven by frequent recombination events during the sexual stage of the parasite's life cycle within the mosquito vector [11]. The presence of multiple MSP1 and MSP2 alleles suggests that individuals are exposed to genetically diverse parasite clones, which is typical of communities with ongoing and widespread malaria transmission [12].

The identification of several MSP2 variants, particularly the predominance of certain subtypes in Bori, may indicate higher transmission intensity or the circulation of more heterogeneous parasite populations in that area. Such patterns have been reported in similar endemic regions, where high multiplicity of infection reflects a stable and mature transmission system [13, 14]. Genotypic diversity has important implications because it influences acquired immunity, treatment outcomes, and reinfection rates. Individuals exposed to diverse parasite strains tend to develop broader but strain-specific immunity, which affects susceptibility to future infections and disease severity.

Furthermore, tracking MSP alleles provides valuable epidemiological information that can guide malaria control programs. Changes in allele frequency over time may signal shifts in transmission, introduction of new parasite strains, or effects of interventions such as vector control or antimalarial drug policy (Holder et al., 1992). Therefore, the demonstration of multiple allelic families in both study locations underscores the importance of maintaining molecular surveillance to detect changes in parasite population structure.

Taken together, the findings of this study highlight the complementary value of integrating different diagnostic approaches for malaria surveillance. While RDTs remain useful for rapid case detection in resource-limited settings, microscopy and PCR provide more accurate assessments of infection burden. Additionally, molecular genotyping offers deeper insight into parasite population dynamics and can serve as a valuable tool for monitoring the effectiveness of malaria control strategies. Strengthening diagnostic capacity and integrating molecular tools into routine surveillance systems would improve the accuracy of malaria burden estimation and support targeted interventions in endemic regions such as Rivers State.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated notable differences in *Plasmodium falciparum* detection across RDT, microscopy, and PCR. The higher prevalence observed in Bori compared to Eleme suggests location-specific variations in transmission intensity, likely influenced by environmental and demographic factors. The detection of multiple MSP1 and MSP2 allelic families further indicates substantial genetic diversity among circulating *P. falciparum* strains in the two communities. This diversity reflects ongoing transmission and exposure to multiple parasite lineages.

Limitations

The study population consisted of febrile patients presenting at health facilities, which may not fully represent infections occurring in the wider community, including asymptomatic carriers who often contribute to sustained transmission. The reliance on a single molecular target for PCR confirmation, while effective for detection, may not capture mixed-species infections if present. Additionally, the genotyping focused only on MSP1 and MSP2, excluding other informative markers that could offer a more comprehensive view of parasite population structure.

Recommendations

The findings of this study demonstrate the need to integrate molecular diagnostic tools such as PCR and MSP genotyping into routine malaria surveillance, especially in settings where accurate detection and monitoring of transmission intensity are essential. Given the high genetic diversity observed, periodic molecular surveillance is recommended to track changes in parasite populations and to detect emerging dominant allelic types. Community-based screening, including asymptomatic individuals, should be encouraged to obtain a more accurate understanding of malaria transmission patterns. Finally, targeted control interventions should be intensified in areas such as Bori where higher infection levels and broader parasite diversity were observed.

Article Information

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

Competing Interests: Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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